

PSYCHOLOGY OF STUDENTS' CHARACTER IN THE WORLD LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

The article depicts the student's character in English literature. The role, genesis, national nature, poetic-typological features and the portrait of students in the works of English literary writers, their character's features, similarities and differences. The article presents samples from English literature, analyzes and studies comparatively and typologically. The comparative study of the works of world figures analyzed in the article will have a positive impact on the development of our international literature and will promote the reading literary books and reading culture.

1. Introduction.

Student image plays a special role in the system of artistic images of world literature. It reflects the outlook, behavior, material and spiritual world of young people in the world. This image points to the future of the society in which that student lives. Student's character plays a special role in the system of artistic characters of world literature. It reflects the outlook, behavior, material and spiritual world of young people in the world. By this character writer points to the future of the society in which that student lives.

In literary works, writers use artistic details to describe the world. Accordingly, artistic detail refers to the smallest pictorial or expressive artistic details: portrait and landscape elements, act, object, and so on. The artistic details can be divided into several groups to make the

analysis easier. First of all, external and psychological details are covered. Their exteriors, which you can easily find in their names, paint us externally, objectively, their appearance and their surroundings. In turn, the external details are divided into portrait, landscape and real. Psychological details reflect a person's inner world, which are separate mental actions: thoughts, feelings, emotions, desires, and so on. External and psychological details are not separated by an inaccessible boundary. The portrait of a literary hero is a variety of artistic details, one of the elements of artistic integrity.

In the center of every work has a person with his or her own complex inner world. Every writer is, in fact, a psychologist, whose task is to open the human heart, to understand the motives of the heroic actions. An artistic character is like a model in which people's complex

relationships are studied. The writer examines his protagonist, leaving him freedom of movement. In each play, the writer uses a series of psychological techniques that allow him to penetrate the inner world of the protagonist in order not to "limit" his protagonists to anything.

Psychology includes the moral principles, aspirations, frustrations, character, attitude to life, complexes, abilities, level of intelligence, personality traits (introvert, extrovert) of the protagonists of the work.

2. Discussion and the results.

The image Rastinyak in O. Balzac's "Father Gorio" of and Raskolnikov in Dostoevsky's Crime and Punishment was also used for comparison.

The the character of students in world literature, its psychological features have been described differently by many writers. Their moral principles, character traits differ from each other. For example, in the book "Under the western eyes" by Evelyn Vaugh, the student protagonist Razumov is portrayed as a sad person. "Razumov doesn't seem to talk much, even when he's deeply affected." One of his personal characteristics is his dislike of women. "What do I have to do with women. I don't care what you think of him. Let them do whatever they want. I'm not interested in them at all. As Razumov charcter Raskolnikov, the protagonist of F. Dostoevsky's "Crime and Punishment", has a character that he does not like human beings. "He was lost in thought, he was deep in thought, he didn't want to see anyone, not just the housewife, he was afraid of meeting someone face to face." [2] Rastinyak, the protagonist of Honore de Balzac's "Father Goriot", is completely different from these two heroes. Both his character and attitude to life are

completely different. He liked to walk among more people, nobles, to walk with ladies. "Realizing the importance of the role of women in society, he made a plan to join the aristocracy in order to find a sponsor. Eloquent young man and chattiness, particularly on these qualities, so it tends to be the woman figure and that would be added to his beauty""[4] This student preferred to choose an easy life for himself. He prefers to live a light life through others rather than through his own labor.

At the same time, one can meet the knowledgeable, intelligent and wise students who live the life of the heroes in the image of the student. Evelyn Waugh's "Decline and fall" "Paul Pennyfezer, for a time, voted with due diligence and caution in elections, evaluated ballet and literary criticism more carefully than others, was intelligent, polite, and fluent in a foreign language." He was one of the most determined young men." [9]

Also, the protagonist of Tom Wolf's "I am Charlotte Simons" Charlotte is portrayed as a well-educated, intelligent, polite girl who went to university on her own. "But I think this time there is an exception to the rule. Really, I can't turn a blind eye to that. Thus, this girl, who received a maximum of sixteen hundred points and five in the four profile tests of her choice, was privileged to receive a presidential scholarship throughout North Carolina." [1] The girl, who was fortunate enough to be a student, could not hide her astonishment. She was very pleased to come to Dupont University. But the culture and character of the students there was not very different from what she expected. "Hooliganism, rudeness, shamelessness, actually half-naked walking - appear in front of strangers on the same towel ... and

drink ... two hours after assistant-tutor Mrs. Ashley warned all freshmen not to have alcohol in the dormitory, the students drank.”[1] To a student who said she would only take knowledge, the situation seemed very strange. Even university professors saw this as a normal situation, and higher education was not what she expected. Student psychology was a lifelong pursuit rather than a completely different education.

We can find a similar situation in the work of another writer. The protagonists of Donna Tart's "The secret history" amaze the reader with the psychology of students and their behavior. The story is told by one of its participants, Richard Paypen. A nineteen-year-old boy who had come from California in those days to study ancient Greek. He miraculously managed to join Julian Morrow's student group of five rich and uneducated young men who were passionate about ancient Greece. For Richard, who is not so rich, new friends open up a completely different, attractive world. In this play we can meet different students as they walk. In this novel we can meet different type of students, their behavior and studies.

1. Drug student. "I used to see Cloak Bunny a little less. Apart from the school years he spent together, his commonalities were few and far between, and he was always wandering around in a half-bohemian party and was completely addicted to drugs. But I didn't notice anything wrong with Bunny's behavior, even if I suddenly noticed him. [10]

2. Alcohol student. "Charles was a polite man and rarely got angry, but he would get angry if he ran against the Catholics. He was also very passionate

about alcohol. In fact, Charles drank a lot.”[10]

3. Homosexual student. Things were even more unpleasant with Francis. It was never mentioned, but we all knew he was gay. He wasn't distinguished by a breakdown in relationships, but he did go to some mysterious "parties" from time to time, and once, on the morning of our acquaintance, he tried to touch me as well. [10]

Thus, in the works of world literature, our writers portray students of different character, aspiring to life, knowledgeable, intelligent, as well as wealthy, greedy, thugs, criminals, drug addicts, alcoholics, homosexuals, perverted students. explained.

4. Conclusion

Previously, Russian higher education institutions did not want the representatives of the nation to study in prestigious higher education institutions, they did not want to go out with a sharp man from within the nation. But despite this, Jora graduated from a prestigious university with his passion and hard work and became a military doctor.

Deep understanding of truth, correct instinct of truth, simplicity, artistic depiction of characters, richness of content, enduring charm of presentation, poetic language, deep knowledge of human heart and modern society, breadth and boldness of brush, power and strength of spirit, luxurious fantasy, aesthetic life abundance, originality - these are the qualities that make this work a whole new world of art. All this forces us to pay full attention to it and to acquaint our readers deeply with it,

to reveal the riches it contains in aesthetic life.

Finally, understanding the deepest layer, one of the ways to penetrate the protagonist's inner world is the work itself: individual episodes, approaching similarity

and contrast of scenes, repetition of plot situations (plot level or presence of external plot elements of the plot, such as biblical legends, parables and other episodes included).

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